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A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“WHISPERS FOR THE HEART”

In moments of Sadness
May you find Goodness
Hope, Strength, Faith, and Love
You are not alone
Family and Friends are there

When you are overwhelmed
Rest, Pause, and even Stop
Take one step at a time
Let go of what troubles you
Let go of what you can't control

When you want to cry
Let the tears flow
As they flow, they bring healing
And after you cry, rest
These are the whispers for the heart

